

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

Welcome to the IN-HABIT APP!

What is the IN-HABIT APP?

A digital application (or app) that acts like a friendly fellow citizen, suggesting fun activities for you to enjoy in your city. It was created by the IN-HABIT project for people living in Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra, and Riga, the four pilot cities involved in the project.

And what's it for?

Well, the app will help the IN-HABIT project better understand the needs of the people in your city, helping them improve the project experience locally, and helping them work to make your city more inclusive. It will also help researchers involved in the project to collect useful data and create innovative models and solutions to roll out in your city and the other pilot cities, and maybe even later across Europe.

The app also aims to boost inclusive health and well-being for people - like you - who use it. It does this by involving users in games, supporting behavioural changes around healthy lifestyles such as healthy diets, sustainable mobility, socialisation, and cultural habits.

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Okay, so how does it work?

First off, how can I access it?

Can I use it with any mobile phone? Do I need to download it?

You can access the web app directly through your internet browser (on any mobile phone or tablet), at this link: <https://inhabitapp.inhabit-h2020.eu/>

There's no need to download anything, and the app is programmed to work on most mobile devices to be as inclusive as possible.

How about on my computer?

Unfortunately not. The app is designed to be accessible from mobile devices only, so you can use it around your city!

Do I need to sign up or log in?

Yes, you'll need to sign up with your email, create a password, and include a few simple pieces of information to begin with. Once your registration is confirmed, just log into your account and you can start!

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So, how do I actually use it in my city?

Once you're logged in, just click the name of your city and you'll be taken to your city page. Find the missions and locations on your city map and start playing! Test yourself with the missions and quizzes, and collect as many badges as you can by completing as many missions as possible. By clicking on a mission title, you'll find out more information about the mission, how to complete it, and the rewards you'll earn.

Yes, but... what is a mission?

Missions are simply actions, big or small, for you to carry out in your city. Each one is related to your local IN-HABIT goals. Some missions can only be done once, while others can be repeated over time. Sometimes, you may need to complete one mission before you can access the next. Find out more.

What different kinds of missions are there?

Quite a few! And they can be achieved in different ways:

GPS missions: go to a specific location in your city and then click on the 'Accomplish Mission' button. Using GPS, the system will detect your location to complete the mission.

QR-Code missions: search for a certain QR-Code in a specific area of your city, as shown on the map, and scan the QR-Code to complete the mission.

Quiz missions: correctly answer a number of questions to complete the mission.

Device-assessed missions: your device will interact with sensors located in your city to complete the mission.

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Surveys: complete the surveys to let us know how you're doing while using the app. This will help researchers find out more about well-being in your city and develop valuable new solutions to roll out.

And what's a reward?

Rewards are a great way for you to keep score of your achievements within the IN-HABIT APP. For each mission you complete, you'll earn a **badge** to show on your profile and a certain number of points. The more missions you complete, the more badges and points you earn!

Want to find out how to get an Explorer badge or a Nature Lover badge? Or maybe you'll get a Know-It-All one! Try the app to find out.

Will I be rewarded in any other way?

Sorry, but no: the use of the app is voluntary and is not rewarded. However, depending on your city, by using the app and completing missions you could unlock tokens to use locally, such as discounts on using public spaces, transportation, museums, or other initiatives.

What about my data?

How will it be used and stored?

All data from the app will be anonymous and used for research purposes. Passwords are irreversibly encrypted to keep them nice and safe. All research related data, such as answers to surveys, will be anonymized and stored on servers that meet the strictest security standards. All other data held is technical data required for the app to work properly, such as the IDs of missions you've carried out or

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badges you've unlocked. No GPS data or other data is stored. What's more, firewalls and other software are used to ensure all your data is really secure.

DEMO - What's the demo for?

The demo version of the app is an initial version with slightly less functionality. It will be used to evaluate how easy the missions are to accomplish, to what extent people are engaging with them, and so on. Multiple technical tests will also be carried out while the app is in its demo version to make sure the final version runs super smoothly.

The demo will be available for a few months in 2023 before the final version of the app is launched. To help us improve the user experience, just use it and let us know what you think: email your feedback to projects@bookonatree.com.

How is it different from the final version?

The demo version has less functionality than the final version. For example, fewer mission types are available: device-assessed missions, for instance, will only be added in the final version.

Sometimes, you may find that a mission has been marked as accomplished even if you're not in exactly the right spot or the picture you've taken isn't correct. This is because we're still working on it - apologies!

At this stage, the only personal data held by the app is your first name, last name, and email address, while more information will be requested in the final version. Don't worry though, your data is already anonymous in this demo.

In the demo version, no tokens for use in your city are available, but badges are.

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Ready to put yourself to the test?
Sign up today and see which badges you can achieve!

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